

Preparation and Properties of EPDM/CNTs composites

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SUMMARY

EPDM/CNTs composites were prepared by using a Brabender mixer with multiwalled CNTs and organo-clay. Organo-clay led to enhancement in mechanical properties of the composites and improved dispersion of CNTs in the rubber matrix as well. TEM and FESEM confirmed that CNTs were well dispersed in EPDM. The CNTs-rubber composites showed characteristic piezo-resistivity.

Keywords: CNT, nanocomposites, rubber, conducting, piezoresistivity.

INTRODUCTION

Recently electrically conducting rubber composites (CRC) with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) filler have received much attention as potential materials for sensors.^{1,2} Upon external forces, CRC deformation takes place with the micro scale change of inter-electrical condition in rubber matrix due to the change of contact resistance, and CRC reveals macro scale piezoresistivity. It was reported that rubber composite sheets filled with highly aligned CNTs resulted in significant improvement in their elastic modulus and thermal and electrical conductivities.³ In this work, we prepared EPDM/CNTs composites with organo-clay co-filler and investigate the morphology and property of the rubber composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounding was performed in Brabender internal mixer with CAM rotor configuration. Cloisite® 15A (Southern Clay Products, USA) was chosen as a nanoclay because it was treated with a non-polar surfactant, 2M2HT, dimethyl dehydrogenated tallow ammonium onto sodium montmorillonite. The nanoclay concentration was kept as a constant weight to EPDM phase, 8.0 wt%, while the multiwall CNT (Aldrich, USA) concentration was varied from 0.9 to 5.5 wt%. Subsequently the compounds were cured with α,β -bis(t-butylperoxy)diisopropylbenzene at 170 °C in a compression mold. The composition of the EPDM compounds are summarized in Table 1. The changes of CRC resistance were measured to find their piezoresistive characteristics with respect to their deformations. Figure 2 shows the experimental setup to measure piezoresistivity of CRC composite on a cantilever. The resistance of CRC was investigated with LRC meter (Hioki 3522) and the beam deflection was measured with laser displacement sensor (Keyence LC-2400A) to find the CRC deformation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the composites were enhanced due to improved dispersion of organo-clay and CNTs in the rubber matrix. The morphology was visually confirmed by means of TEM and FESEM images. From the TEM images of Figure 1, it is clear that the CNTs dispersed in rubber matrix very well at 3, 4 and 7 wt%.

Figure 2. TEM images of EPMD/CNT composite with different concentration of CNT (a) 3 (b) 4 and (c) 7wt% of CNT.

The CRC having piezoresistivity showed linear resistance change with respect to its deformation. There is an interesting thing that resistivity of the composite surface increases in both of the cases, either elongation or compression with the increasing of the wt% of the CNT in the composite. It is anticipated that the piezoresistivity of CRC can be eligible to develop a flexible sensory composite whose resistance is linearly variable under deformation, pressure and shear force.

Figure 2. Experimental setup to measure piezoresistivity of EPMD/CNT composite on a cantilever with respect to the beam deflection.

Table 1. Data for Compounding (part)

	EPDM	Nanoclay	CNT
NC0	100	8.8	0
NC1	100	8.8	1
NC2	100	8.8	2
NC3	100	8.8	3
NC4	100	8.8	4
NC5	100	8.8	5
NC6	100	8.8	6
NC6	100	8.8	7

References

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